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Review Article

A Review on Medicinal Plants with Anti- Ulcer Activity

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ABSTRACT

The field of herbal medicine has grown exponentially in the past several years and due to their natural origins and low side effects, these medications are becoming more and more popular in both developed and developing nations. Anti – ulcer activity of medicinal plants is scientifically evaluated by in – vitro and in – vivo studies. The healing effects of medicinal plants come from the fact that they accommodate a wide range of secondary metabolites, called phytochemicals, which can be synthesized again and again in nature. The richest sources of active metabolites are contained in seeds, bark, roots, leaves, and fruits of plants. Therefore, a multitude of plants have employed these phytochemicals as a defense mechanism against pathogens. These components are classified as alkaloids, tannins, carotenoids, flavonoids, terpenoids, glycosides, and saponins. While the majority of research concentrated on pharmaceutical action in animal models, many botanical compounds have been shown to have antiulcer activity.

INTRODUCTION

In the last few years there has been an exponential growth in the field of herbal medicine and these drugs are gaining popularity both in developing and developed countries because of their natural origin and less side effects. The World Health Organization (WHO) has listed 21,000 plants, which are used for medicinal purposes around the world. Among these 2500 species are in India, out of which 150 species are used commercially on a fairly large scale. India is the largest producer of medicinal herbs and is called as botanical garden

of the world. A gastric ulcer is a type of peptic stomach ulcer. A duodenal ulcer is one which develops in the duodenum. When the stomach or duodenum walls become damaged by the acids that aid in food digestion, peptic ulcers result. Infection with the *Helicobacter pylori* bacteria is the most frequent cause. Long-term use of non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), such as ibuprofen and aspirin, is another factor. Although they don't cause ulcers, stress and spicy meals can exacerbate them. A gastric ulcer is a type of peptic stomach ulcer. A duodenal ulcer is one that occurs

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in the duodenum. When the stomach or duodenum walls are harmed by the acids that aid in food digestion, peptic ulcers result. Infection with *Helicobacter pylori* is the most prevalent cause, followed by long-term use of non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) like ibuprofen and aspirin. Stress and spicy meals do not cause ulcers, but they might exacerbate them [1,2]. Natural products from plants are a rich resource used for centuries to cure various ailments. The use of natural medicine in the treatment of various diseases like peptic ulcer is an absolute requirement of our time [3,4].

Symptoms of Ulcers –

The stomach is location to gastric ulcers, which are painful and prevalent in the elderly population. Eating could make pain worse instead than better.

Weight loss, nausea, and vomiting are possible additional symptoms. Even though the production of acid is normal or reduced in persons with gastric ulcers, ulcers can still develop when there is no acid at all [5]. Patients with duodenal ulcers, which are located near the beginning of the small intestine, are awakened from sleep by excruciating pain and a burning sensation in the upper belly. Pain usually starts when the stomach is empty and goes away after eating. Duodenal ulcers primarily affect men and are more common in younger people. Both the anterior and posterior walls of the duodenum may develop ulcers [6]. In some cases, peptic ulcer can be life threatening with symptoms like bloody stool, severe abdominal pain, and cramps along with vomiting blood [7].

Medicinal plant having anti – ulcer activity:

Sr.No	Plant name	Family	Part used	Extracts	Active constituents	Reference
1.	Acacia arabica	Mimosaceae	Gum	Aqueous	Phenolic compounds, tannins, and flavonoids	8
2.	Terminalia chebula	Combretaceae	Fruits	Methanolic	Tannins, gallic acid, chebulinic acid, and sorbitol	9
3.	Adansonia digitata	Malvaceae	Leaves	Fresh juice	Gum and albuminoids	10
4.	Aegle marmelos	Rutaceae	Fruit	-	Flavonoids, tannins, and saponins	11
			Leaves	Aqueous		12
5.	Aloe vera	Liliaceae	Leaves	Aqueous	Barbalin, isobarbolin, and saponins	13
6.	Allium sativum	Liliaceae	Bulb	Bulb juice	Volatile oil, alliin, and allicin	14
7.	Annona squamosa	Annonaceae	Leaf	Aqueous	Tannic acid	15
8.	Azadirachta indica	Meliaceae	Leaf	Nimbidin fraction	Stearic and palmitic acid	16
9.	Bauhinia variegata	Caesalpiniaceae	Root	Ethanollic, Aqueous	Flavonoids	17
10.	Careya arborea	Myrtaceae	Stem, bark	Ethanollic	Tannins and saponins	18
11.	Carica papaya	Caricaceae	Seed	Aqueous	Chymopapain and papain	19
12.	Ficus religiosa	Urticaceae	Leaves	Hydro alcoholic	Flavonoids, saponins, and tannins	20

13.	Hibiscus rosa sinensis	Malvaceae	Roots	Aqueous	Flavonoids and quercetin	21
14.	Mangifera indica	Anacardiaceae	Flower	Decoction	Mangiferin	22
15.	Mimosa pudica	Fabaceae	Leaves	Ethanollic	Alkaloid mimosine	23
16.	Momordica charantia	Cucurbitaceae	Fruit	Alcoholic, aqueous	Flavonoids, saponins, and sterols	24
17.	Moringa oleifera	Moringaceae	Leaves	Alcoholic	Quercetin, beta sitosterol, and beta carotene	25
18.	Ocimum sanctum	Lamiaceae	Leaves	Oil	Eugenol	26
19.	Phyllanthus niruri	Euphorbiaceae	Aerial part	Metanolic	Alkaloids-4-methoxy-securinine, ellagic acid, beta sitosterol, gallic acid, and hypophyllanthin	27
20.	Psidium guyava	Myrtaceae	Leaf	Methanolic	Quercetin, guaijaverin, flavonoids, and galactose-specific lecithins	28
21.	Rhus coriaria	Anacardiaceae	Leaves	Hydro alcoholic	Flavonoids and tannins	29
22.	Sesbania grandiflora	Fabaceae	Leaf	Ethanollic	Tannins and saponins	30
23.	Shorea robusta	Dipterocarpaceae	Resins	-	Ursolic acid and amyirin	31
24.	Solanum nigrum	Solanaceae	Leaf	Aqueous	Flavonoids	32
25.	Tamarindus indica	Caesalpiniaceae	Seed coat	Methanolic	Tannins	33
26.	Tagetes erecta L.	Asteraceae	Flowers	Hydroalcoholic (Methanol-Water)	Carotenoid lutein	34
27.	Punica granatum	Punicaceae	Flower	Ethanollic	Phenol	35
28.	Nicotiana tabacum	Solanaceae	Leaves	Ethanollic	Alkaloid	36
29.	Glycyrrhiza glabra	Fabaceae	Roots	-	Glycyrrhizin acid	37
30.	Taraxacum officinale	Asteraceae	Roots	Aqueous	-	38

CONCLUSION:

Medicinal plant products are traditionally used in many countries for treatment of Ulcer. Due to the effectiveness, fewer side effects and relatively low-cost herbal drugs are prescribed. The present review has presented comprehensive details of antiulcer plants. Substance and extracts isolated from different natural sources plays important role

to treat ulcer problem. All of the remedies presented here had adequate evidence from traditional or scientific source for their efficacy in management of ulcers. There are various medicinal plants and their extracts (containing active chemical constituents, e.g., tannins and flavonoids) that have significant antiulcer activity in in vivo experiments on animal models. The

combination of traditional and modern knowledge can produce better drugs for the treatment of peptic ulcer with fewer side effects.

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